

in these mixtures. Molar polarization of chlorobenzene in cyclohexane is linear even at great dilutions indicating the absence of complex formation between chlorobenzene and cyclohexane.

The complexes in mixtures, of chlorobenzene + *o*-, +*m*-, and +*p*-xylenes, may not be formed due to dipole association because excess polarizations, P^E , are positive in these mixtures.

P_{12} is a linear function of $(\epsilon - 1)^2/(\epsilon + 2)^2$ which shows that no chemical interaction occurs between the components of the solution. It is expected that only contact-pairs are present.

P^E is again a linear function of $x(1-x)$ for chlorobenzene + *o*-, +*m*-, and +*p*-xylenes which indicate the presence of contact-pairs⁹ in these mixtures. It is expected that contact-pairs may be formed between the vacant 3d orbitals of chloro group in chlorobenzene and π -electron cloud of benzene ring in xylenes.

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Temperature Dependent Paper Chromatography of Co(II), Ni(II), Fe(III), Zn(II) and Mn(II)

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TEMPERATURE dependent paper chromatographic separation has been carried out by many workers¹⁻⁶. The results indicate that the speed of resolution is improved by increasing temperature.

The purpose of this communication is to employ the known solvent systems *viz.*, (i) acetone : HCl : water (87 : 8 : 5)⁷, (ii) acetone : HCl (97 : 3)⁸ and (iii) acetone : HCl : IBMK (85 : 5 : 10)⁹ to study the separation of different cations (a) Co(II), Ni(II) and Fe(III), (b) Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) and (c) Co(II), Ni(II) and Mn(II) at different temperature.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR quality. The usual spraying reagents¹⁰ were used to locate the cations. The solvent mixtures used were (i) acetone : HCl : Water (87 : 8 : 5), (ii) acetone : HCl (97 : 3) and (iii) acetone : HCl : IBMK (85 : 5 : 10). Thermostatic bath with an automatic temperature control was employed to attain a desired temperature. Whatman No. 1 paper was used in glass jar for running the chromatogram.

5.0 μ l of the mixture of the cations *viz.*, (a) Co(II), Ni(II) and Fe(III), (b) Co(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II), and (c) Co(II), Ni(II) and Mn(II) was enacted in the chromatographic separation.

Results and Discussion

The R_f dependence of various cations on temperature in solvent mixture acetone : HCl : water (87 : 8 : 5) resulted the Table-1, the perusal of which shows that in all cases R_f of Ni(II) remains almost constant from 0° to 35° and increases slightly from 35° to 40°. R_f of Fe(III), Zn(II) and Mn(II) show same

TABLE-1 TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF R_f OF CATIONS, FOR SOLVENT MIXTURE ACETONE: HCl : WATER (87:8:5), TIME = 90 MIN.

System	Ions	R_f value at different temperatures(°C)						
		0	10	15	20	30	35	40
1	Ni(II)	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.15
	Co(II)	0.26	0.35	0.40	0.45	0.46	0.69	0.77
	Fe(III)	0.89	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.96
2	Ni(II)	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.19
	Co(II)	0.27	0.38	0.41	0.50	0.52	0.70	0.87
	Zn(II)	0.89	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.95
3	Ni(II)	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.15	0.21
	Co(II)	0.35	0.37	0.46	0.58	0.61	0.83	0.87
	Mn(II)	0.82	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.95	0.25

behaviour with slight increase in R_f from 0° to 10° and running with solvent front above 10°. This tendency of these three ions to move along with the solvent front depends upon the quality of paper, the nature of the solvent and the temperature at which the experiment is conducted. R_f of Co(II) increases from 0.2 at 0° to about 0.8 at 40° which means that Co(II) has a tendency to reach solvent front as the temperature rises. Thus, separation in all the three cases is improved by increase in temperature. However, after 35°, Co(II) reaches Fe(III), or Zn(II) or Mn(II) as the case may be, thereby after 40° the separation of these ions may become impossible as suggested by earlier workers^{1,11}.

A change in temperature influences the rate of movement of the mobile phase as investigated by Muller and Clogg¹². The rate of movement of given cation and hence its R_f value depends upon its

partition coefficient between the stationary phase and mobile phase. This basic idea of Martin et al.^{1,2,14} and Wark¹⁵ resulted the equation :

$$\left(\frac{d \ln \kappa}{dT}\right)_F = \Delta H/RT^2 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where κ = the partition coefficient.

$\Delta H = H_s - H_m$ = Heat of partition required to transport one gm. mole of the solute from stationary phase to mobile phase. A solution of this expression combined with the equation of Martin and Synge^{1,2} gives a relationship given by Bate-Smith and Westall¹⁶.

$$R_m = \log\left(\frac{1}{R_f} - 1\right) = \frac{-\Delta H}{2.303RT} + K \dots \dots (2)$$

where K is an arbitrary constant.

The plots of R_m vs. $1/T$ are linear over a temperature range -5° to 40° indicating its applicability. The plots exhibit positive slope assigning negative values to the heat of partition (Table-2). Table-2 suggests that the ΔH for Fe(III), Zn(II), and Mn(II) are zero. This might be due to not holding equation (2) in these cases. However, for Fe(III), Zn(II) and Mn(II), increase in R_f from 0° to 10° can be predicted with the small increase in ΔH , which remains constant above 10° as evinced by their movement along with the solvent front (Table-1).

TABLE-2 HEAT OF PARTITION OF CATIONS, FOR SOLVENT MIXTURE ACETONE : HCl : WATER (87 : 8 : 5), TIME=90 MIN.

System	ΔH value in KCal/mole				
	Fe(III)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Zn(II)	Mn(II)
Fe(III) + Co(II)	0.0	-9.64	0.0	-	-
+ Ni(II)					
Zn(II) + Co(II)	-	-9.57	0.0	0.0	-
+ Ni(II)					
Mn(II) + Co(II)	-	-9.61	0.0	-	0.0
+ Ni(II)					

Practically zero value of ΔH for Ni(II) in all three systems would mean that at equilibrium the partition coefficient approaches a unit value and the concentration of species equals in both the phases. The tendency to pass over from one phase to another should remain unaffected by variation in temperature. Thus, practically zero value of ΔH for Ni(II) and high instability of its chloro complex leads Ni(II) to remain at its original position. There is apparent increase in R_f value of Ni(II) from 35° to 45° which might not be due to migration of Ni(II), but as temperature increases, solvent gets evaporated and thus solvent front does not rise much. This causes apparent increase in R_f .

A relatively higher value of ΔH for Co(II) in all three systems indicates its tendency to pass into mobile phase from stationary phase with an increase in temperature. Increase in R_f of Co(II) with increase in temperature supports this idea (Table-1).

Investigation of the system (a) Co(II), Ni(II), and Mn(II) in solvent system acetone : HCl (97 : 3) reveals that R_f of Ni(II) remains constant over the studied temperature range. R_f of Mn(II) changes from 0.75 at -5° to 0.98 at 20° and thereafter attaining unit value at higher temperature. Thus, this system shows clear separation from -5° to 15° after which Co(II) touches Mn(II). This tendency of Co(II) and Mn(II) of passing together above 15° indicates their equal ΔH values.

It was observed that R_f values of Ni(II) remain practically constant (0.03) within the temperature range of 0° to 30° in all three cations systems, in the solvent system acetone : HCl : IBMK (85 : 5 : 10) as although there is slight apparent increase in R_f beyond 30° (0.05) as discussed earlier. All the three cations viz. Fe(III), Zn(II), Mn(II) have similar tendency to pass along with the solvent front at all temperature. The R_f values of Co(II) in all the three systems increase with the temperature (0.40 to 0.80) at 0° to 30° respectively and it was observed that Co(II) has a tendency to attain unit value of R_f beyond temperature 30° .

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